

Identification of Consumer Characteristics of Arabica Coffee Shop in Banda ACEH

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Abstract:- The purpose of this research is to identify consumers' characteristic in selecting the Arabica coffee shops in the city of Banda Aceh, Indonesia. The sample used in this study was determined based on the random sampling method that consist of 10 coffee shops, with 30 people determined as the sample per coffee shop across the city of Banda Aceh. As a result, this research discovers that the consumer characteristics that influence decisions in choosing Arabica coffee shops in Banda Aceh City based on gender characteristics are as follows, 67% male and 33% female, based on age characteristics 20 to 29 years (78%) followed by age 30 to 39 years (22%), based on the level of education S1 (59%), followed by Masters (17%), high school/equivalent (14%) while the minority educated S3/D3 (10%) and based on occupation obtained as many as (48 %) of respondents are dominated by respondents who work as entrepreneurs, (24%) private employees, (12%) government employees and the rest (14%) are housewives, unemployed and students.

Keywords:- Consumer characteristics, Arabica coffee

I. INTRODUCTION

Coffee shops in Aceh offers a unique characteristic that separate itself from other regions in Indonesia. Usually, coffee shops in Aceh are equipped with a meeting and discussion space where people across gender, age, and occupation can exchange information and cultural abbreviation across the coffee shop (Engel et al (1994). In addition, the art of coffee drinking in Aceh has transform into a cultural norms and has become famous as the land of 1001 coffee shop (Warsidi , 2019). However, the unique characteristic of Acehnese culture in coffee drink has present a questionable clue on which characteristic of people in Aceh that are more drawn into a coffee culture in Aceh. Griffin (2005) argues that loyal consumers have 4 characteristics, namely: (1) make regular purchases of products; (2) accustomed to consuming the product; (3) recommend the product to others; (4) not easily influenced by other products. This study aims to identify and study the characteristics of Arabica coffee consumers in the city of Banda Aceh Indonesia.

II. RESEARCH METHODS

The instruments used _ in research This is a questionnaire, where the questionnaire or questionnaire used here is in the form of statements relating to the factors that influence consumer decisions in choosing Arabica coffee shops. The questionnaire used in this study was a Likert scale.

Population and Sample The research was conducted in ten Arabica coffee shops in Banda Aceh City which were selected using method *purposive sampling* . The coffee shop that was sampled was a coffee shop that served Arabica coffee made by baristas with an espresso machine. Another criterion is the coffee shop with the largest number of customers who are the *market drivers* in Banda Aceh. From each coffee shop, 10 customers were interviewed by *random sampling* so that the total number of respondents was 100 people . Meanwhile, to describe the characteristics of the respondents identified in this study were the respondents of Arabica coffee shops in Banda Aceh, namely gender, age, last education, and occupation.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

- *The Current Condition of the Coffee Trade in Banda Aceh*
Coffee shop trade in the city Banda Aceh has not developed rapidly if investigated since 1974 . _ After the tsunami, the new coffee shop became an *icon* in Aceh as a whole, especially in the city of Banda Aceh . Moment This coffee shop has been found everywhere across the city of Banda Aceh . Many coffee shop entrepreneurs pop up and try with make a profit in the business . Coffee shops in the city of Banda Aceh have developed with various variants, such as there are coffee shops that make robusta coffee blends as typical coffee shops and there are also those that use Arabica coffee blends as a sales strategy to attract customers. Aceh coffee shop when this already Becomes power pull traveler moment visit to Aceh and make Aceh continue known with the distinctive taste of the coffee.
- *Respondent Characteristics*
Characteristics of respondents identified from Arabica coffee shop respondents in the city of Banda Aceh are gender, age, last education, and occupation.

➤ Gender

Based on gender, the majority of respondents are male (67%) and the rest are female (33%) (Figure 1).

Fig 1:- Gender

The number of male consumers is in accordance with the results of research from Fadli & Kusno (2020) those who conducted research on Kiwari coffee shops. The study also stated that although drinking coffee is dominated by men, basically men and women have the same goal in consuming coffee at the coffee shop, namely as a distraction activity to relax and meet acquaintances. The dominance of male consumers in coffee shops compared to women is due to the form of habits in daily life that are often done by men (Utama & Yuliawati, 2020).

➤ Age

Characteristics of respondents based on age obtained in this study were respondents aged 20 to 29 years (78%) followed by age 30 to 39 years (22%). Coffee shop consumers in terms of age are now experiencing a shift, in the past, coffee connoisseurs in coffee shops only came from the elderly.

Fig 2:- Age Range

The increasing consumption of coffee at a young age is inseparable from the style of today's society who likes to gather in coffee shops. According to Nurikhsan (2019), there are several motivations behind teenagers to drink coffee in coffee shops, namely: (1) to relax themselves; (2) a place to gather with friends; and (3) internet access in a coffee shop. In addition, the convenience and concept of a coffee shop make the main attraction for young people to choose to drink coffee at a coffee shop.

➤ Education

Characteristics of respondents based on their education obtained in study the majority have bachelor's degree education (59%), followed by master's degree (17%), high school/equivalent (14%) while the minority have doctoral degree education (10%).

Fig 3:- Last Education

Research conducted by Fadli & Kusno (2020) also found that consumers of Arabica coffee shop Manglayang Karlina were dominated by people with an undergraduate education. Decisions in the choice of daily consumption can be determined by a person's education level. Someone who has a higher education background makes them more broad-minded and open to new things that happen in society, as well as in choosing to drink coffee in coffee shops that are currently booming. Consumers with higher education are able to analyze well in consuming a product (Savira & Prihtanti, 2019; Utama & Yuliawati, 2020).

➤ Work

Before collecting data, the variable of employment status is the type of work, as in general in identifying the characteristics of respondents. But after the data was collected, the respondents were divided into several categories, namely government employees, private employees, entrepreneurs, students/students, housewives, not working. The characteristics of coffee connoisseurs according to occupation in this study were obtained as many as (48%) of respondents were dominated by respondents who worked as entrepreneurs, (24%) private employees, (12%) government employees, as many as (3%) were housewives, did not work. (7%) and students (6%).

Fig 4:- Type of Work

The number of consumers with self-employed jobs is in line with the results of research by Suisa & Febrilia (2014) who conducted research on the coffee drinking lifestyle at the coffee bean & tea leaf plaza tunjungan surabaya. The results of his research stated that consumers who drank coffee at the coffee shop were dominated by people who were entrepreneurs, male, aged 21-30 years, and had a diploma/S1 education.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the study research, based on the gender perspective, it shows that consumers of Arabica coffee shops in Banda Aceh are generally male with a percentage of 67% compared to the female with 33% of the total respondent, based on the age characteristics the highest percentage is 20-29 years with a percentage of 78% of the total respondent. Meanwhile, the level of education reveals that undergraduate student are more drawn into a coffee shop (59%). While In the category of employment rate, the self-employed are the dominant respondent compared with the rest of the data (48%).

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